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DESIGN AND APPLICATION OF E-LEARNING TO ENHANCE QUALITY AND ACCESSIBILITY TO EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Advent of Internet made modern world like a global village, and it has reduced the distances between the learner and teacher. A learner can use e-learning to take education not only for a limited period of time but for the whole life thus e-learning facilitate continuing and life long education. This article deals with the Design and Application of E-learning to Enhance Quality and Accessibility to Education and also makes learning materials accessible to learner. E-Learning also supports the concept of classrooms without walls where learner and facilitator have the flexibility to make contact with each other, 24 hours a day, 7 days a week; this develops Social Networking, Collaboration and Self learning among learner, which helps in effective learning.

DEFINITION OF E-LEARNING

E-learning is a broader concept; it is defined in terms of technologies used for the purpose of teaching and learning. The word E-Learning consists of two words "e" and "learning", where "e", stands for the word "electronic" i.e., electronic devices and "learning", means acquisition of knowledge, skills and attitudes. Thus E-learning means

acquisition of knowledge, skills and attitude through the use of technology, like Internet, mobiles, PDA's and Computers. Carliner defines online learning as "educational material that is presented on a computer". In chapter "Designing online learning", Sharma, S (2009), defines online learning as an "Internet or Intranet-based teaching learning system designed for web based delivery, without face to face contact between teacher and learner"; in this type of teaching learning system knowledge is imparted through synchronous and asynchronous modes through Internet or intranet. According to Badrul L Khan "E-learning represent open, flexible and distributed learning".

SCOPE

E-learning, though in its nascent stage, has a very high scope, because of rich and interactive content. In developing countries like India there is a huge disparity in education of rural and urban areas, this disparity can be removed by online education, which will reduce cost and gives learner an opportunity to get higher education.

ADVANTAGES

E-Learning is beneficial to the learner and facilitator because it is cost effective,

saves time, available 24 hours a day and 7 days in a week. Following are some of the advantages of E-learning:

- 1) E-learning has the advantage of conducting classes anytime and anywhere thus it reduces the constraint of Space and Time. In synchronous online learning interaction between learner and facilitator is in real time, where as in asynchronous online learning interaction between learner and facilitator is not in real time.
- 2) E-learning provides rich and interactive resources such as text, pictures, graphics, animation, games, database, audio, videos and simulations to learner.
- 3) In traditional teaching money is spent in travelling, but e-learning provides education to learners from any geographic location, hence it saves money on travelling and it is cost effective.
- 4) E-learning caters to the needs of gifted learners, average learners and slow learners by making them to learn according to their own pace and capacity.
- 5) E-learning provides opportunities to learners to learn by designing course according to their needs, ability and learning styles.
- 6) Collaborative learning and cooperative learning increases motivation, persistence and develops interpersonal and communications skill among learner (Fisher Phelps &

Ellis, 2000; Gokhale, 1995).

- 7) Help learners to access learning resources such as a database or course content online via an Internet or the intranet, according to their own abilities and interest.

LIMITATIONS

According to Swamy. K. (2010), the technology enables learner to have all kinds of interactions virtually but there is an emotional disconnect which is the essence of human relationship.

Following are the limitations in e-learning;

- 1) Learners should have knowledge and skills in using computers and accessing Internet, otherwise learning environment will become threatening.
- 2) Low bandwidth imposes restrictions in accessing web 2.0 technologies, and also courses with HD videos and animations require high bandwidth, this may frustrate learners and they may give up course.
- 3) Frequent load shedding may interfere with accessing course.
- 4) There is an emotional disconnection between learner and facilitator in online learning.
- 5) Costly hardware' and software' are required in designing and delivering online courses.

ISSUES RELATED TO E-LEARNING DESIGN

Mr P. Kabilan (2010) rightly quoted about instructional designing, "Software and hardware are only vehicles in the creation of an environment that is conducive to learning".